

Kinetics of Adsorption of Ionic Surfactants at Alumina-Water Interface[†]

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Adsorption of ionic surfactants from solution on the alumina-water surface has been studied as a function of time. Adsorption seems to be almost complete in about 20 minutes. Attempt has been made to understand the mechanism of the adsorption process. Adsorption being diffusion controlled, the diffusion coefficient of the surfactant micelles were determined from the kinetic data. Diffusion coefficient values were found to increase systematically with increase in the chain length of the surfactants. An empirical equation has also been proposed which fits the kinetic data well.

THERE has long been a growing interest in understanding the physicochemical aspects of adsorption of surfactants, proteins, lipids, bile salts *etc.* at various types of interfaces¹⁻⁵. Adsorption of ionic surfactants from solution is generally time-dependent even when highly purified adsorbing materials are used. Garner and Mina⁶ have shown that the surface diffusion coefficient of the surfactants is dependent upon the number of carbon atoms present in the amphiphiles. Very recently Graham and Phillips⁷ have shown that the rate of change of surface concentration of the protein at the air-water interface is diffusion controlled but at higher surface coverages there exists an energy barrier.

Although large number of studies have been reported on the adsorption of ionic surfactants at the interfaces, no systematic study of adsorption kinetics has been done to throw light on the mechanism of the adsorption process. In the present paper, an attempt has been made to study the kinetics of adsorption of cationic and anionic surfactants at the alumina-water interface. Attempts have been made to understand the role of diffusion in the adsorption process and to calculate the diffusion coefficients of the surfactant micelles from the kinetic data. An empirical equation that fits the kinetic data has also been proposed.

Experimental

Alumina powder (E. Merck) used was of chromatographic grade of high purity. It was thoroughly washed with deionised water and dried overnight in air-oven at 100-105° to a constant weight before the experiment.

Highly purified surfactants, *viz.* sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS), cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB), myristyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (MTAB) and dodecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide

(DTAB) were used, which were obtained as gifts from Dr. K. S. Birdi of the Danish Technical University. The curves indicating variation of the surface tension of water in the presence of increasing concentrations of the surfactants did not exhibit any minima. CMC's of the surfactants measured from conductivity experiments were in agreement with the values reported in literature⁸. Water used throughout the experiment was deionised and distilled from alkaline potassium permanganate solution. The aqueous media used were phosphate buffers of ionic strength 0.125 for pH 6.0 and 8.0, whereas acetate buffer of ionic strength 0.125 was used for pH 4.0. All inorganic salts used were of analytical grade.

Determination of surface area of adsorbent: The surface area of the adsorbent alumina powder was determined by measuring the adsorption of palmitic acid from benzene solution on the adsorbent. The method was same as described elsewhere⁹ and the value was found to be $61.62 \pm 0.38 \text{ m}^2\text{g}^{-1}$.

Measurement of adsorption kinetics: A stock quantity of buffer or salt solution of definite pH and ionic strength was prepared, which was treated as a solvent for the preparation of the solution of surfactant. Then the solutions of the respective surfactants near the CMC values were prepared with this solution by the appropriate dilution in a standard joint wide-mouth bottle of capacity 200 ml. Alumina powder (4-5 g) was weighed accurately and poured into the solution bottle and immediately the whole solution was shaken carefully avoiding the formation of foam and the stopwatch was started. The solution (2.0 ml) was then withdrawn after 2 min interval and stored in test tubes. After each withdrawal, the system was shaken thoroughly for a few seconds and then the powder was allowed to settle. Solutions were withdrawn after complete settling of alumina

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(complete within ~ 1 min) so that only clear supernatant was withdrawn. The whole set of experiment was carried out in a water-bath at $30.0 \pm 0.2^\circ$.

The collected surfactant solutions after proper dilution were analysed by the dye-partition technique¹⁰. For this, a dye methylene blue in 0.01 N HCl or a vinyl disulphine blue in 0.01 N H₂SO₄ were used to form cationic and anionic dye-surfactant complexes respectively. The concentration of the dye was usually kept 100 mg dm³. Partition was carried out between an aqueous electrolyte solution and an organic chloroform layer for the extraction of dye-amine complex. A definite volume of the coloured solution was taken in a Klett tube with the help of a long needle glass syringe and the absorbancy of the amine-bound dye in chloroform layer was measured in a Klett Summerson colorimeter using red filter. The extraction of the dye-bound surfactant with chloroform was done at constant temperature by keeping the bottles inside a thermostatic bath. From the comparison of this absorbancy with those of the blank containing known concentrations of the surfactant, the concentration of the surfactant was estimated within 3-4% error.

Calculation of amount adsorbed as a function of time : If C_1 be the initial concentration and V_1 be the initial volume of the surfactant solution, then considering the mass balance with respect to surfactant, one can write,

$$\frac{C_1 V_1}{1000} = \frac{C_1 (V_1 + V_w)}{1000} + \Gamma_R^1 \cdot W \quad (1)$$

where, C_1 = final molar concentration of the solution after time t_1 , V_w = volume of solution (ml) withdrawn, V_1 = volume of solution (ml) left after time t_1 , Γ_R^1 = amount (mole) adsorbed per gram after time t_1 , and W = weight of the alumina powder taken in gram.

After a second step of withdrawal of some volume V_w from the solution at time t_2 , one can write,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{C_1 V_1}{1000} &= \frac{C_1 (V_1 + V_w)}{1000} + \Gamma_R^1 \cdot W \\ &= \frac{C_2 (V_2 + V_w)}{1000} + \frac{C_1 V_w}{1000} + \Gamma_R^1 \cdot W \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

where, C_2 = final molar concentration of the solution after time t_2 , V_2 = volume of solution (ml) left after time t_2 and Γ_R^2 = amount (mole) adsorbed per gram after time t_2 .

Thus, after n times withdrawal at time t_n , are can write,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{C_1 V_1}{1000} &= \frac{C_1 (V_1 + V_w)}{1000} + \Gamma_R^1 \cdot W \\ &= \frac{C_2 (V_2 + V_w)}{1000} + \frac{C_1 V_w}{1000} + \Gamma_R^1 \cdot W \\ &= \frac{C_n (V_n + V_w)}{1000} + \frac{C_{n-1} V_w}{1000} + \frac{C_{n-2} V_w}{1000} + \dots \\ &\quad + \frac{C_2 V_w}{1000} + \frac{C_1 V_w}{1000} + \Gamma_R^n \cdot W \quad (3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_R^n &= \frac{C_1 V_1}{1000 W} - \frac{C_n V_n}{1000 W} - \frac{V_w}{1000 W} \\ &\quad (C_1 + C_2 + C_3 + \dots + C_n) \\ &= \frac{1}{1000 W} [(C_1 V_1 - C_n V_n) - V_w \sum C] \text{ mol g}^{-1} \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the amount adsorbed per gram at any time t was calculated with the help of equation (4). From the knowledge of surface area of the alumina powder and utilising equation (4) the amount Γ_R^n (equal to Γ_R) of a surfactant adsorbed in millimole per square meter of alumina was calculated.

Results and Discussion

The extents of adsorption, Γ_R of the cationic and anionic surfactants at the alumina-water interface as a function of time are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Fig. 1 shows the time variation of Γ_R for cationic surfactants at pH 6.0 and anionic surfactant SDS at pH 4.0. It is found from the Figs. that for DTAB, MTAB and SDS, the adsorption is

Fig. 1. Plot of Γ_R vs t for CTAB, DTAB, MTAB (phosphate buffer, pH 6.0) and SDS (acetate buffer, pH 4.0) at 30° , $\mu = 0.125$ (NaCl)

almost complete within 20 min. For CTAB with an initial concentration of 10×10^{-4} mol dm³, the completion of adsorption requires about 1 h. The different values of Γ_R at the state of completion of this kind is of course a function of final equilibrium concentration of the surfactant in the bulk. At pH 8.0 (Fig. 2), adsorption is almost complete within 30 min for all the cationic surfactants.

The rate of adsorption of a solute from solution at an interface usually depends on several factors. The adsorption of ionic surfactants at the alumina-water interface depends primarily on the rate of arrival of the surfactant molecules at the interface. The surfactant molecules approach the interface from the bulk through diffusion and get adsorbed

Fig 2 Plot of Γ_R vs t for CTAB, MTAB and DTAB (phosphate buffer, pH 8.0) at 30° ; $\mu=0.125$.

at the interface. Hence, such adsorption, at least the initial stage of adsorption will be diffusion controlled. The concentrations of the surfactants used for the kinetic study were higher than the respective CMC of the surfactants. So the rate of adsorption will be dependent on the rate of diffusion of micelles at the interface.

At the initial stage of adsorption, the energy barrier for the approach of the micelle or surfactant molecule towards the interface is zero, i.e. the activation energy to the adsorption at the surface is zero. The amount adsorbed at the interface is then related to the diffusion coefficient D and time t by the equation^{11,12}

$$\Gamma_R = 2C_R \left(\frac{Dt}{3.142} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5)$$

where, C_R is the substrate surfactant concentration. It is further assumed that C_R remains essentially constant during the adsorption process and t is the time of adsorption.

The present kinetic data has been well fitted to this equation by plotting Γ_R against $t^{1/2}$. Such plots are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. It is seen from these figures that Γ_R bears a linear relationship with $t^{1/2}$ upto certain time after which it deviates from linearity. Such deviations were also observed for the kinetics of adsorption of proteins at interfaces⁷. The deviation is possibly due to the

fact that as more and more surfactants get adsorbed, the substrate concentration C_R decreases and cannot be considered constant. From the linear portion of the plots, diffusion coefficient of the surfactant micelles have been calculated from the slopes of the curve. The values of the diffusion coefficients of ionic surfactants at different pH are shown in Table 1.

The diffusion coefficient values, as seen from Table 1, are of the order of 10^{-9} to 10^{-12} $m^2 s^{-1}$. These orders are in good agreement with micellar diffusion coefficient values reported in literature¹⁴. It is also known that the migration velocity of the adsorbable molecules or ions is a function of the number of carbon atoms. Usually the surface diffusion coefficient value increases rapidly with an increase in the number of carbon atoms. The overall adsorption rate is a function of chain length only and not of the nature or the position of the hydrophilic end group¹⁵. In our results too (Table 1), we find the same trend. For DTAB, at pH 8.0, D is of the order of 10^{-12} , for MTAB 10^{-11} and for CTAB 10^{-9} . Similarly at pH 6.0, diffusion coefficients is least for DTAB bearing of the order of 10^{-11} . For MTAB, it is of the order of 10^{-10} and for CTAB 10^{-9} . For SDS, micellar diffusion coefficient is of the order of 10^{-10} $m^2 s^{-1}$ at pH 4.0. Thus we see that the overall adsorption rate is a function of chain length, a conclusion similar to that made earlier by Shinoda *et al.*⁵.

Fig 3 Plot of Γ_R vs $t^{1/2}$ for CTAB ($\Gamma_R=1 \times 10^4$), MTAB ($\Gamma_R=1 \times 10^3$), DTAB ($\Gamma_R=1 \times 10^3$), (phosphate buffer pH 6.0) and SDS ($\Gamma_R=1 \times 10^3$ acetate buffer, pH 4.0) at 30° , $\mu=0.125$

Fig 4 Plot of Γ_R vs $t^{1/2}$ for CTAB ($\Gamma_R=1 \times 10^4$), MTAB ($\Gamma_R=1 \times 10^3$) and DTAB ($\Gamma_R=1 \times 10^3$), (phosphate buffer, pH 8.0) at 30° ; $\mu=0.125$.

It is also interesting to note that the adsorption kinetic data were fitted in good agreement in an empirical type of equation,

$$\frac{dC_R}{dt} = k(C_R)^n \quad (6)$$

TABLE 1—VALUES OF DIFFUSION COEFFICIENTS (D) OF IONIC SURFACTANTS

Surfactants	pH 4.0 ($\mu=0.125$)	pH 6.0 ($\mu=0.125$)	pH 8.0 ($\mu=0.125$)
	D m^2s^{-1}	D m^2s^{-1}	D m^2s^{-1}
SDS	1.00×10^{-10}	—	—
CTAB	—	2.16×10^{-9}	4.71×10^{-9}
MTAB	—	2.86×10^{-10}	8.13×10^{-11}
DTAB	—	8.38×10^{-11}	6.11×10^{-11}

where, k and n are two constants. This equation demands a linear plot of $\log dC_R/dt$ against $\log C_R$. Such plots are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. From the slope and intercept of these plots, the empirical constants n and k has been found out and reported in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF n and k FOR IONIC SURFACTANTS AT DIFFERENT pH

Surfactants	pH 4.0		pH 6.0		pH 8.0	
	n	k	n	k	n	k
SDS	1.3	0.11	—	—	—	—
CTAB	—	—	1.4	1.8	1.7	10.1
MTAB	—	—	1.3	0.11	1.4	0.41
DTAB	—	—	4.0	120000	5.0	50000

Fig. 5. Plot of $\log dC_R/dt$ vs $\log C_R$ for CTAB, DTAB, MTAB (phosphate buffer, pH 6.0) and SDS (acetate buffer, pH 4.0) at 30° , $\mu=0.125$.

Fig. 6. Plot of $\log dC_R/dt$ vs $\log C_R$ for CTAB, DTAB and MTAB (phosphate buffer, pH 8.0) at 30° , $\mu=0.125$.

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